

**OPTIMIZATION OF URBAN ECOLOGY
(IN THE CASE OF THE CITY OF JIZZAKH)**

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Annotation. An average of 28,000-30,000 tons of pollutants are emitted into the atmosphere of Jizzah city per year, which is 0.9% of the total pollutants emitted in the Republic. In the city, there is a decrease in the emission of pollutants from both industry and transport. The main reason for this is the replacement of dust removal equipment for economy, the reduction of industrial production, the transfer of vehicles to harmless gas fuel, the replenishment of urban transport with new modern vehicles.

Keywords: industrial enterprise, environmentally friendly, technology, problem, dust cleaning equipment, safety, ecological.

Introduction. The city of Jizzakh is located in the lower part of the Sangzor river, in the area of the plain on the slopes of the mountains and slopes of the Jizzakh region. land area - 100 sq. km, population - more than 150 thousand people. The climate of the city of Jizzakh and its surroundings is continental, characterized by cold winters and hot, dry summers.

Protection of atmospheric air from pollutants emitted by industrial enterprises, and underground and surface water from wastewater is one of the urgent issues of the

present time and is of universal importance. One of the most important directions is to study the process of pollution of the environment with waste and wastewater.

Protection of the environment from production and consumption waste, waste water, atmospheric air pollutants is inextricably linked with the problems of rational and complex use of natural resources and implementation of environmentally friendly technologies.

From the time when man saw the face of the world, he felt how much he harmed the environment by polluting the environment with the waste of the products he consumed, with sewage, and with various pollutants in the atmosphere. introduced, but could not fully solve these problems at the threshold of the 21st century.

Statement of the problem and research method. The growth of the urban population, the concentration of industry in a limited area, is the reason for the deterioration of the ecological conditions in populated areas, especially in large cities.

On average, 28,000-30,000 tons of pollutants are released into the air of the city per year, which is 0.9% of the total pollutants released in the Republic. In the city, there is a decrease in the discharge of pollutants from both industry and transport. The main reason for this is the replacement of dust cleaning equipment with efficiency, the reduction of industrial production, the transfer of motor vehicles to harmless gas fuel, and the filling of city transport with new modern vehicles.

Research results and their discussion. One of the problems of every city is the issue of waste. Every year, 50,000 tons of household waste, 2,800 tons of solid and 0,248,000 tons of (toxic) industrial waste from organizations and enterprises are generated in the city. One of the unresolved issues in the city is the lack of timely disposal of waste. The fauna and flora of Jizzakh city is unique. Existing trees in urban neighborhoods and surface water ditches for watering them are not evenly distributed.

The city of Jizzakh consumes about 28.8 thousand m³ of drinking water per day. All this is obtained from underground water sources. Despite the shortage of drinking water, it is allowed to be used for other purposes in the city. In the following years, it

is observed that drinking water is used for washing cars, for saunas, and in the production of building materials.

Because for this purpose it is possible to use re-purified technical or sewer water. Many car washes do not have a water circulation system, and used, polluted wastewater is dumped into sewers, ditches and canals without further treatment.

For years, the issue of connecting the sewage system of the "Zilol" neighborhood to the main network of the city "Suvokova" enterprise has been unresolved. As a result, wastewater is dumped into the natural environment without treatment.

It is necessary to solve the following important issues in order to reduce the pollution of the natural environment from waste, sewage, atmospheric air with pollutants:

- Phase out the use of ethylated gasoline. Full transition of vehicles to ecologically safe fuel types;
- Updating the city's motor vehicle fleet with vehicles that meet the requirements of global environmental safety standards, ensuring the gradual transition to standard requirements;
- Modernization of existing productions, introduction of a new modern cleaning system in city enterprises, replacement of outdated dust and gas cleaning equipment;
- Ensuring operation and modernization of "Suvokova" enterprise, taking into account the perspective development of the city. Provide 100% sewerage in order to prevent discharge of waste water into open bodies of water in the city. Active introduction of a new scientific research system and circulating water supply to city enterprises and organizations. Stop the operation of car washes without circulating water supply;
- Organization of greening activities on the banks of the Sangzor River and streams flowing through the city;

- Timely transportation of household waste collected in temporary waste storage areas in the city, neighborhoods, production waste in production and industrial enterprises to the city landfill;
- Among the general public, in all educational institutions, enterprises and organizations, it is necessary to strengthen the propaganda work on environmental protection and effective use of natural resources.

Conclude

Implementation of several important measures to optimize the ecology of Jizzakh city: rational use of clean drinking water, ensuring the full efficiency of Jizzakh city "Wastewater Treatment Plant", timely transportation of waste to landfills, beautification of all areas of the city accelerating greening works, protecting atmospheric air (using innovative technologies in the implementation of dust-gas cleaning equipment, switching cars to gas fuel, updating the traffic structure, implementing the national program to reduce greenhouse gas emissions) as a result of the implementation of measures, the principle of stabilization of the ecological situation in the field of atmospheric air protection is generally observed. It is necessary to achieve technical re-equipment of the main sectors of the economy, introduction of new technologies, as well as stabilization and reduction of pollutant emissions into the atmosphere.

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